

CONTEXTUALIZING CULTURE IN OLATUNBOSUN TAOFE EK'S *WHERE IS PATIENT ZERO?*, FUNKE AKINDELE'S *A TRIBE CALLED JUDAH*, AND STEVEN SPIELBERG'S *THE TERMINAL*

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ABSTRACT

*Culture is critical to national development. Accordingly, this paper explores the various dimensions of culture as encapsulated in Olatunbosun Taofeek's *Where is Patient Zero* (2022), *A Tribe Called Judah*, by Funke Akindele, and *The Terminal*, a 2004 American comedy-drama film produced and directed by Steven Spielberg. Key concepts are articulated to further broaden understanding of the subject matter.*

KEYWORDS: Culture, National development, Olatunbosun Taofeek and *Where is Patient Zero*

INTRODUCTION

Culture is a complex subject. The complexity of the subject matter results from the varied usage of the term. Accordingly, it has received enormous attention from scholars worldwide, and several definitions have been proffered to help better our understanding of the concept. However, for the paper, Tylor's (1871) definition of culture as “that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society” has been adopted by the researcher. By this definition, culture is viewed as a quality possessed by all people in all social groups, which is transmitted from one generation to another. In its usage in this paper the term “society” includes such human groupings as the community, social groups, clubs, professional bodies, ethnic nationality, a country, and the world at large.

Derivatives of experience learned or created by the individuals of a population, including those images or “increments” and their interpretations (meanings) when transmitted from past generations, from contemporaries, or formed by individuals themselves constitute culture in their right (Schwartz 1992). This gives credibility to the universally held concept that culture is dynamic. Brown (1963: 3) corroborates this definition, asserting that culture encapsulates “all the accepted and patterned ways of behavior of a given people.” It encompasses the social behavior, institutions, and norms found in human societies, as well as the knowledge, beliefs, arts, laws, customs, capabilities, and habits of the individuals in these groups (Tylor 1871). These shared commonalities unite

these individuals as a group and help to distinguish them from other groups.

Theatre draws its existence and feeds from the culture of the society. The origins of theatre itself can be traced back to ancient civilizations in Egypt, Greece, and Rome, where performances were held in amphitheaters and other public spaces. These early forms of theatre often included elements of music, dance, and poetry, and were often used to celebrate religious festivals or tell stories from mythology. Brockett and Hildy (1968) explain that "rituals typically include elements that entertain or give pleasure, such as costumes and masks as well as skilled performers. As societies grew more complex, these spectacular elements began to be acted out under non-ritualistic conditions. As this occurred, the first steps towards theatre as an autonomous activity were being taken." Perhaps this is what Styan (1960) meant when he asserts that, "The miracle of the theatre is that the community and a people have agreed to let drama happen." This further demonstrates the symbiotic relationship between the theatre and culture.

In attempting to contextualize culture, I have selected one (1) play - Olatunbosun Taofeek's *Where is Patient Zero* (2022), and two films. One of the films, *A Tribe Called Judah*, is a 2023 Nigerian film produced by Funke Akindele, while *The Terminal* is a 2004 American comedy-drama film produced and directed by Steven Spielberg.

Where is Patient Zero?

The play has been regarded as one of the finest plays on the international politics of disease that threatens the existence of humans and the economy. It explores the politics of disease control, the menace of rogue scientists, and global conspiracies. The play was longlisted for the Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Prize for Literature and was shortlisted for the Association of Nigerian Authors (ANA) Drama Prize 2022.

Synopsis of the Play - *Where is Patient Zero?*

Where Is Patient Zero describes the attempt to cover the initial carrier of Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) known as patient zero. With Dr Damsi parading himself as the messiah of the period, he skits and rolls with the rogue scientists covering their iniquitous in ASTRONAUT 666: a lethal potent network prepared to be inserted into humans as a form of vaccine to have access to human brains as a motor neuron control to the billions of people inhabiting the world. The aim is to connect every human brain in a single interface at the speed of a millisecond.

In their scientific exploration is the intrusion of Thanatos, the spirit of death, and his brother, Hypnos in escalating the negative part of their experiment and the eventual emergence of an uncontrollable virus. The virus quickly spreads down to Africa where we have Babanka the sitting president of a populous country in Africa. He messes up the entire plans against the virus in his country as he uses the pandemic to get aid and grants hence threatening to permanently lock down his country's universities and by extension researchers, whom he accuses of not being cerebral like their Western counterparts. He declares lockdown and encourages spiritual procedures to fight the virus.

Things are not working while government agencies use the lockdown as a cash-out to the detriment of the masses. The masses eventually revolt against the lockdown out of hunger and frustration. Johnson and Sadiq, who are foreign agents sharing contraceptives to the

masses to avoid population explosion, face the masses' wrath.

Eventually, Babanka gets Dr Damsi to his country to help him smuggle the latest vaccine for himself and other politicians. He gets infected and later survives. Then he concludes on the entire virus prevention while talking to his Minister of Health: “The government will give you money to build a laboratory. You guys will also create a virus. Then we spread it. Later, we bring our vaccines out. We make billions of dollars through our vaccines. We shall do it in a grand style. The virus business is not for 'those guys' alone. After this conversation, you move into action. I want our version of COVID that we shall use to freeze the whole world.”

The Minister is not convinced about the project, then Babanka declares the name of his new virus as “Zazuvirus” boasting that the virus has the potency of disturbing anybody anywhere in the entire world. However, he warns his minister and “his scientists” that as no one uncovers Patient Zero of coronavirus no one should know the source of zazuvirus when out from Africa.

A Tribe Called Judah

A Tribe Called Judah is a 2023 Nigerian film produced by Funke Akindele and starring Funke Akindele, Timini Egbuson, Jide Kene Achufusi, Uzee Usman, Tobi Makinde Olumide Oworu, Genoveva Umeh, Nse Ikpe Etim, Juliana Olayode, Uzor Arukwe, Fathia Balogun, Yvonne Jegede and many others (Erezi 2023). The film was released to cinemas nationwide on December 15, 2023. Akindele has said the film is dedicated to her late mother and draws partially from her mother's life (Ileyemi 2023).

Synopsis of *A Tribe Called Judah*

A Tribe Called Judah tells the story of a single mother, Jedidah Judah (played by Funke Akindele), who has five sons from five different fathers from five different tribes. The first two sons are responsible and try their best to work and support their mother. Meanwhile, the last three are less helpful: Pere (played by Timini Egbuson) is a chronic pickpocket, Shina (played by Tobi Makinde) is a hoodlum and tout in the community; and the last, Ejiro (played by Olumide Oworu), is naughty and only cares about his girlfriend, Testimony (played by Genoveva Umeh). Despite their bad behavior, Jedidah continues to support them and get them out of trouble.

Things take a turn for the worse when Jedidah develops chronic kidney disease, needing ₦18 million to fund her operation and ₦400,000 weekly for her dialysis. The first son, Emeka, loses his job, and the five sons see no other option than to rob Emeka's ex-boss, who is rumoured to be a money launderer, to get the money to save their mother's life (Stephen 2023). However, their plans take a dramatic turn when they encounter armed robbers at the scene.

The Terminal

The Terminal is a 2004 American comedy-drama film produced and directed by Steven Spielberg and starring Tom Hanks, Catherine Zeta-Jones, and Stanley Tucci. Partially inspired by the true story of the 18-year stay of Mehran Karimi Nasseri in Terminal 1 of Paris Charles de Gaulle Airport, France, from 1988 to 2006 (Ethan 2004), the film is about an Eastern European man who is stuck in New York's John F. Kennedy Airport terminal when he is denied entry to the United States and at the same time is unable to return to his native country because

of a military coup.

The film was released in North America on June 18, 2004, to generally positive reviews and was a commercial success, earning \$219 million worldwide.

Synopsis of *The Terminal*

Viktor Navorski (Tom Hanks) arrives at JFK International Airport but finds that he is not allowed to enter the United States. While he was en route to the US, a revolution was started in his home nation of Krakozhia. Due to the civil war, the United States no longer recognizes Krakozhia as a sovereign nation and denies Viktor's entrance to the US. Unable to leave the airport or return to Krakozhia, Viktor instead lives in the terminal, carrying his luggage and a mysterious Planters peanut can.

Customs and Border Protection (CBP) Head Frank Dixon (Stanley Tucci) wants Navorski removed from the airport. Navorski collects money for food by retrieving vacant baggage trolleys for the 25-cent reward from the machine until Dixon prevents this. He then befriends a catering car driver named Enrique (Diego Luna) who gives him food in exchange for information about a female Customs and Border Protection officer (Zoë Saldana), whom Enrique is infatuated with. With Viktor's help, Enrique and Dolores eventually marry each other. He meets flight attendant Amelia Warren (Catherine Zeta-Jones), who asks him out to dinner, but he tries to earn money to ask Amelia out instead. He finally gets an off-the-books job as a construction worker at the airport earning \$19 an hour.

Viktor is asked to interpret for a desperate Russian man with undocumented drugs for his sick father. Viktor claims it is "goat medicine," barring the drug from confiscation and resolving the crisis. Under pressure and the watchful eye of the Airport Ratings committee, which is evaluating Dixon for an upcoming promotion, Dixon has a falling out with Viktor. Though Dixon is advised that sometimes rules must be ignored, he becomes obsessed with getting Viktor ejected from the airport. An airport janitor, Gupta Rajan (Kumar Pallana), exaggerates the "goat" incident to his co-workers and as a result, Viktor earns the respect and admiration of all of the airport staff. One day, Viktor explains to Amelia that the purpose of his visit to New York is to collect an autograph from the tenor saxophonist Benny Golson. It is revealed that the peanut can Viktor carries with him contains nothing more than an autographed copy of the "Great Day in Harlem" photograph. His late father was a jazz enthusiast who had discovered the famous portrait in a Hungarian newspaper in 1958 and vowed to get an autograph of all the 57 jazz musicians featured in the photograph. He succeeded in obtaining 56 but died before he could finish his collection. A few months later, the war in Krakozhia ends, but Dixon will still not allow Viktor to enter the United States. Amelia negotiated an emergency visa for Viktor through her friend, a married government official with whom she had been having an affair. Efforts by Viktor to frustrate his entrance into the United States failed as his staff were disillusioned with him, collaborating to help Viktor fulfill his dream.

Contextualising Culture in Olatunbosun Taofeek's *Where is Patient Zero*, Funke Akindele's *A Tribe Called Judah*, and Steven Spielberg's *The Terminal*

Having articulated the concept of culture, and having introduced the play and films to be used in this conceptualization, I will delve into the unique cultural elements portrayed in each work.

Olatunbosun Taofeek's *Where is Patient Zero* explores cultural realities within the

context of a pandemic. Drawing from Brown's (1963) definition of culture as comprising “all the accepted and patterned ways of behaviour of a given people”, we see Taofeek (2022) mirrors the societal attitude, belief system, tradition, leadership, crisis response mechanism, approach to healthcare, and emergencies.

From the title of the play, the pattern of dependence on foreign philosophical thrust, theoretical framework, and products by the Nigerians is brought to the fore. The term “patient zero” first emerged in the United States in the 1980s when researchers were attempting to understand how HIV/AIDS was spreading in the community. In a study looking at the sexual contacts of gay men infected with AIDS, researchers labelled one person in the sexual network as patient “O” — which stood for Outside California. They were placed at the centre of the diagram and linked to several other cases. This letter O was later misread as the numeral 0 (Billis and Bullen 2020). Later, this patient zero was revealed to be a French-Canadian flight attendant named Gaetan Dugas. He was subsequently, and incorrectly, blamed for setting off the entire US AIDS epidemic. While the researchers never suggested Dugas was the source of the outbreak, and research later confirmed the virus entered the US long before he did, the idea of patient zero stuck. Shits (2000), an American Journalist amplified the usage of the term, deploying the usage in his work on HIV and AIDS. McKay (2020) attributes the linguistic linkage of the phrase to the 20th-century military expressions such as “zero hour” - when action begins, “ground zero”- the point below where a bomb detonates as patterns that further amplified the excitement around the phrase. None of the seminal incidents was situated or had bearings in Nigeria. Even THANATOS – the transmigrator of souls and HYPNOS – his twin brother are spiritual elements from Greek mythology, despite the rich repertoire of spiritual elements in Africa. LADY in ACT IV in rejecting condoms tells her audience; “Are you surprised, I do oral sex, fingering, and sometimes I use sex toy...” (p24) which of course are part of the borrowed patterns to African sexual realities. BABANKA, the President reported going to the Gambia, Senegal, Cameroon, and India to get spiritual powers (p76).

Taofeek shows that although President BABANKA seems to know much about the 'white man's way' and the virus conspiracy, there were no proactive measures in place to prevent the virus from hitting his country. This resonates with the attitude of leaders in our country. Despite their education, experience, and role expectations, in most cases, we are confronted with a low-level interest or capacity in exigency planning, system thinking, and resource mobilization. This is a sharp contrast with the cultural presentations of the “white man,” who is shown in the play as fighting to topple each other as global leaders, in science, medicine, weaponry, etc., with DR DAMMY's country already exploring options to reduce the world's population, also to control everyone using the ambitious “ASTRONAUT 666,” which upon completion would be able to tell and interpret the thought level of everyone, and can even scan the future of individuals telling what each individual is capable of doing. This contrasts sharply with the no-plan situation in Taofeek's *Where is Patent Zero's* country where even the relief materials meant for the masses are hoarded leading to a protest that results in the looting of warehouses. This is a reminiscence of Nigeria's COVID-19 experience, where relief materials including money were stashed away in several locations across the country, of how the masses who could no longer resist the hunger exacerbated by the lock-down embarked on a mass protest and looting spree that led to the vandalization of several governments and private warehouses of known politicians.

Someone once said, “If you can survive in Nigeria, you can survive anywhere in the world.” Taofeek celebrates the resilience of his people showcasing its various patterns. From

young people represented by GUY and OSONDU who resisted the HFC's "sexual control palliative" in ACT IV to MADAM in ACT VII who braced the lockdown, continuing her drinks and pepper soup business, to even JOHNSON and SADIQ who explored every opportunity to only make a living, but the be relevant in their families during the pandemic, they all demonstrated the real Nigerian spirit. We are also another dimension of resilience in the character of BABANKA – "the President of the most populous country in Africa." He messes up the entire plans against the virus in his country as he uses the pandemic to get aid and grants hence threatening to permanently lock down his country's universities and by extension researchers he accuses of not being cerebral like their Western counterparts. He declares lockdown and encourages spiritual procedures to fight the virus. Eventually, Babanka gets Dr Damsi to his country to help him smuggle the latest vaccine for himself and other politicians. He gets infected and later survives. Then he concludes on the entire virus prevention while talking to his Minister of Health: "The government will give you money to build a laboratory. You guys will also create a virus. Then we spread it. Later, we bring our vaccines out. We make billions of dollars through our vaccines. We shall do it in a grand style. The virus business is not for 'those guys' alone. After this conversation, you move into action. I want our version of COVID that we shall use to freeze the whole world" (p119).

Love and romance are shared aspects of our humanity, or what is referred to as "cultural-universal." However, one's society and the social environment of individuals play a significant role in determining how these are expressed. COVID-19 and the resultant lockdown had a significant impact on the norms, values, and patterns of expression. Despite the pandemic and the lockdown imposed by the government, we find this manifestation of love by LOVER BOY and LOVER GIRL in ACT IV. Their exchanges pass for one of the best enchanting tales of the lockdown and I take the liberty to recapture a part of it here:

LOVER GIRL: I love you with the whole of my heart.

LOVERBOY: My dear, I see you in my life every day and COVID cannot scare me or steer me away from you.

LOVER GIRL: Last night, I vowed I shall not depart from you even if the restriction embraced all living souls.

LOVERBOY: Really? My heart bleeds for you and tempts me to die for you, not for COVID but because of true love.

LOVER GIRL: Really!

LOVER BOY: Because of you the bad time of COVID has become the pizza of my soul. Keeping hope alive amidst the raging storm without helping hands.

We shall strive to live, survive, and forever stay together as a lemon.

LOVER GIRL: And we shall make lemonade of life.

LOVERBOY: Even the lockdown cannot lock down my love for you! (PP25-26)

One can't help but admire the enchanting narrative of the lovers, and the risk they take to stick together out there, despite the enforcement of social distancing and lockdown by the government and its agents. We see patients at the isolation centre find love, with some patients in isolation getting pregnant.

The language of the play reflects the rich cultural heritage of Nigeria and the diversity of her culture. Taofeek deployed English being the official language for communication in

weaving the play's narrative. Pidgin, a Nigerian version of the English language is also deployed to articulate the class of the educational and social class of the characters. Proverbs and metaphors are used to situate the play in the rich Nigerian cultural milieu.

Religion and spirituality are essential parts of the "cultural universal." Across most cultures, there is a belief in the profane, physical world, sacred, and the extra-mundane or the supernatural world also of the involvement of the supernatural in the affairs of man. Phrases such as "it is an act of God", "divine intervention," "curse, punishment from gods," etc., point to this belief. This clarifies Tylor's (1970) definition of religion as the "belief in spiritual beings." Expanding Tylor's definition, James (1902), in his book *The Varieties of Religious Experience*, asserts that religion is "the feelings, acts, and experiences of individual men in their solitude, so far as they apprehend themselves to stand concerning whatever they may consider the divine".(any godlike object, whether it is a concrete deity or not) to which the individual feels impelled to respond with solemnity and gravity." Such acts may include rituals, sermons, commemoration or veneration (of deities or saints), sacrifices, festivals, feasts, trances, initiations, matrimonial and funerary services, meditation, prayer, music, art, dance, or public service.

The world religions (Christianity, Islam, Judaism, Hinduism, and African Traditional Religion) vary in the degree they demand the exclusive loyalty of their adherents, "and no one of the religion is a single entity (Brown 1963)." Taofeek serves these nuances by contrasting the characters, ALUFA BULALA and IMAM LAHIRA, APOSTLE KOBI, and PASTOR AKIARA. IMAM LAHIRA would rather commit suicide than let the bill for online worship centres to fly. He is open about his distrust for the government and its policies accusing the government of constituting a legal terrorist against the people. He is accusing Ameriko, the Sunnis movement, and Saudia of conspiracy in the proposed bill to abrogate physical worship thus:

IMAM LAHIRA: Rather than the bill to go through, I shall kill myself, astaghfirullah (I ask for forgiveness from Allah)! We know this law is coming from the Ameriko with the support of the Saudia and they want us to follow it like chickens. I am a Shiite, a follower of Abu Bakr. I don't believe and can't follow the Sunnis. So if any Muslim wants to follow that useless bill, let them follow, for us Shiite, we shall not!

APOSTLE KOBI and PASTOR AKIARA also exhibit the entities within Christendom and their diversities with APOSTLE KOBI cutting the picture of the self-styled General Overseer (GO) of the 21-century mega-church, who is responsible to no other person except himself. Rather than the conventional priestly vestments, he is dressed in a designer's blazer, with chains on his neck. He does not see anything wrong with the proposed bill for online worship/Spiritual centres. He sees it more from the perspective of financial and material gains, reduction of the Church's workforce, and other dependencies (pp 54-55). This is a sharp contrast to the values of PASTOR AKIARA's Church. His decorum and mien set him apart. Even when he disagrees with APOSTLE KOBI, he simply tells him, "I am sorry Apostle Kobi, you are wrong!" In the face of harassment and intimidation by APOSTLE KOBI, he can maintain his balance and demonstrate courage. His address to the public hearing is concise and straight to

the point, “I am against online religious centres! (pp55). Notice that he is speaking not just for his Church, or the Church alone for that matter, but for every religion. Having a working understanding of the various religions and the differences between entities within a culture could enhance group cohesion, peaceful co-existence, and development.

In the play, BABANKA consults with various native priests and goes forward to deploy the spiritual approach in his effort at pandemic prevention. The naming convention deployed by Taofeek in the play points the audience to the religious inclination of the characters, thus we have names like, “JONATHAN, “PASTOR AKIARA”, “APOSTLLE KOBI” and “PRIEST” representing the various entities of the Christian faith, while IMAM LAHIRA, ALUFA BULANA, and SADIQ encapsulate the attitude, beliefs, and values of their Muslim's counterpart. THANATOS and HYPNOS are spirit beings – the god of darkness, and his sleep counterpart whose involvement in the conspiracy broadened the death toll from the pandemic on the masses. THANATOS and HYPNOS showcase the extra-mundane realities of the relationship between man and the forces beyond him. DEBICA the herbalist holds back to us the attitude, patterns, and nuances within the practice of the traditional African religion. Claiming powers that practitioners may not possess, fetish practices, the challenges of dosage estimation for medications, lack of documented pieces of evidence, desecration of human lives, financial exploitation, and lies associated with the practice are unpacked in the play.

During the lockdown, scarce resources were mobilized to organise conferences as part of the government's effort to control the pandemic. Each speaker took time to intellectualise the pandemic and advance the itinerary of the blame game. However, no resolution was captured from any of the conferences. This resonates with Iguanre's (2000) position that we are always involved in talk-talk, with nothing to show.

The film "A Tribe Called Judah" offers insights into Nigeria's cultural bouquet, focusing on familial ties, cultural diversities, resilience, traditional values, or societal norms, and the fusion of modernity with traditional values within a specific community. It explores patterns in cultural evolution and the challenges faced by individuals and societies navigating cultural shifts.

Despite the huge population, over 500 languages, the expansive landmass, and all the challenges facing the country, Nigeria is portrayed more as a resilient country and fits more within the collectivist mold when viewed through the cultural lenses of *A Tribe Called Judah*. The group cohesion, loyalty, and communalism in Judah's family are thought-provoking. They live together and will always be there for each other no matter the situation. In the various instances where their mother is harassed, exploited, or under attack, the family would respond at the speed of light to contain the situation. They almost killed Daddy Michael in one instance but not for their mother's intervention. In another instance, they would mobilise all the creativity, resources, knowledge, and connections fighting to keep their mother alive from her kidney failure and dialysis. All of them have significant respect for their mother despite her history, lifestyle, poor status, and stigma within the community. Judah though, not very rich would be supporting other members of her community for self-actualization. She is leasing her Keke to young people to try and make a living; she is helping young women start small businesses while providing financial support to others. In one instance, Ejiro and Testimony

are caught swindling by pretending to be beggars and soliciting arms from the unsuspecting members of the community. Later Jedidah Judah is seen giving the confiscated money to a vulnerable woman in the community to pay WAEC fees for her child, despite the challenges in the Judah's family. She is reported to have provided the money Linda used to start her pepper and tomatoes business. Testimony is using her brother's vehicle to “do small runs to raise funds to support Jedidah's treatment. Even the yam the mother brought her from the village is shared with friends.

The larger community in *A Family Called Judah* is further segmented into smaller socio-economic groups, and whether it was Judah's family, the community, the gangs, the security operatives, or the C&K Furniture, one could see group loyalty, respect for their leaders, and cooperation. As a way of reinforcing these values, there are consequences for everyone who deviates from these values. Two staff members in C&K Furniture were shot dead for stealing their boss's dollars. Despite Pedro's overwhelming need for money, he is not able to disobey the gang leader's directive not to engage with the security forces standing between them and the N300, 000.00 levies from the landlady raising a new building in their neighbourhood. The community youth almost burnt Pere for stealing, but not for the quick intervention of the mother and Linda. This aligns with Hofstede's (XXX) element of collectivism – showcasing the closely knitted social framework, cooperation, and robust loyalty to the group's hierarchy. However, a new pattern is buttressed in the film – where fidelity is confronted by the bond of love and the need for human survival. Ejiro and Testimony in the film, are two love birds reminiscent of Shakespeare's (1974) *Romeo and Juliet* in deviance from the hierarchy in their pursuit of love. We see them begging for alms together to support Ejiro's work, we see her bring the brother's vehicle to help Ejiro 'make some runs' to support the family. Later we are to see Testimony dancing at the costume party with Ejiro, also at the crime scene as she saves Judah's family from complete elimination following the armed robbery attack and counterattack at the C&K Furniture. What would have separated them finally would have been the secret migration of Judah's family to Aba to escape the wrath of the law, but that wouldn't be, as we see Testimony in the end, eloping with Judah's family.

Pere's deviance against the directive of the gang leader was because he needed funds by all means to support the mother's medical bills. Emeka and Adamu – the supposed “good men” of Judah's family are opting in and joining to rob their boss of dollars to save the life of their mother.

Religion – belief in and worship of a superhuman power or powers especially a God or gods - plays a critical role in *A Tribe Called Judah*. Jedidah would pray and anoint the photographs of her children each morning before going out. We find the “Lord's Super” backdrop behind the wall as the sons are exploring options to raise resources to sort their mother's dialysis (1.00.36 -1.04.27). The belief is further given breath to by the Chairman, CEO of C&K Furniture on hearing of the Jedidah's medical condition and of Emeka's solicitation for a loan for her medical bills. He retorts: “Sickness will never be our portion.” This vividly captures the low-risk perception associated with the belief in miracles and supernatural coverage. Rather than give Emeka support or a loan, he is taking Emeka through a litany of affirmations. He tells Emeka, “Don't you know that the power of life and death are in the tongue... say that she will live, she will not perish...” (0.44.25-52). Instead of Emeka's account number, he is asking for the name of his mother which he plans to give to his wife to add to a prayer list. We also see the Chairman telling Emeka “The Lord will go before you and fight your battles” when Emeka appeals his sack from the company by Collete - the manager at C&K Furniture,

for going to see the sick mother at the hospital without prior authorization. The brothers in blaming him for not stealing dollars from the Chairman, query his reasons with Pere asking "... you be Jesus' assistant?" (1.00.42-1.01.042).

The names of the characters in the film also give out the religious alignment of the people. Jedidah for instance is a Biblical name - the mother of Josiah, the king of Judah (2 Kings 22:1). She was the wife of King Amon of Judah. Judah on the other hand is one of the twelve tribes of Israel and the lineage of Abraham, Solomon, David, and Jesus. Jesus Christ himself is referred to as the "lion of the tribe of Judah" (Revelations 5:5).

The reality of poverty and inequality in the Nigerian culture is again affirmed in the film. More than half of the Nigerian population grapples with extreme poverty, while a small group of elites enjoy the bulk of the nation's ever-growing wealth. Oxfam articulates on the issue as follows:

"In Nigeria, the scale of economic inequality has reached extreme levels, and it finds expression in the daily struggles of the majority of the population in the face of the accumulation of obscene amounts of wealth by a small number of individuals. While more than 112 million people were living in poverty in 2010, the richest Nigerian man will take 42 years to spend all of his wealth at 1 million per day."

The cardinal problem appears to be that of endemic corruption, misplaced priorities, or the lack of direction – what needs to be done by the leadership to change the paradigm. The Chairman of C&K Furniture represents the rich oligarchy in *A Tribe Called Judah*. He is corrupt, an expert in money laundry, and very selfish. He lives in great wealth. The C&K Furniture is only a front for his money laundry business as he is not depending on what sales are made from there.

The poor masses are represented by Jedidah and her "WA-ZO-BIA-MO-BO" family of five children from five men, from 5 ethnic groups in the country, none of whom is appropriately employed. Jedidah is doing everything possible to break the poverty cycle but is constrained by several factors. Her marriage to 5 men from 5 tribes in Nigeria articulates these realities. A sexual abuse survivor at the age of 17, she gave birth the Emeka. Along the line, she met Sanni, but the family was against him marrying a Yoruba woman, more so with a history of a previous child from another father, and Adamu himself having a young girl in Kano betrothed to him. Boma, Pere's father reportedly died one year father the marriage. Her number 4 husband was a lesson tutor for Jedidah's children, to obligate the duty of a father figure Jedidah married him. He was to later run away with all her life's savings including her inheritance from Boma. The fifth partner was Jedidah's drinking partner in her moment of depression.

In sexual exploitation and abuse, people use their position of power to exploit the vulnerability of their survivors. Sexual exploitation and abuse are human rights violations based on gender inequality intersecting with all social inequalities (UN 2022).

Jedidah despite her situation is supporting others in the lower throng of the society by leasing out her tricycles to young graduates like Joseph to eke out a living. She supported Linda in starting her "pepper and tomatoes business" and paying the WAEC fee for Lateefah.

Studies have shown that deprivation and economic inequality provide the incentives for an increase in crime and gangsterism. In the film, *A Tribe Called Judah*, the linkages are laid bay through the activities of Jedidah's children, Pere, Shino, and Ejiro. The three of them were raised by their mother, whereas Emeka and Adamu were raised by their grandmother in

Aba and auntie Mary-Jane in Kano respectively. Pere is almost burned alive for stealing, Shina, a secondary school dropout, and a gangster, and Ejiro, a pickpocket and swindler. The Chairman's boys shot death a boy in the C&K Furniture for stealing the Chairman's money. Collete's account of her involvement in the robbery incident opens another perspective on the issues of inequalities, poverty, and crime. She was a repentant criminal, having promised the mother on her deathbed not to continue in robbery. However, she did not cut off her relationship with her partners. She was informed by her friends of the boss' involvement in money laundry, the huge hard currencies in the shop where she is the manager, and their plan to rob the shop and steal the money. The mix of the sustained friendship with criminal-minded persons, information, and the selfishness of the Chairman must have combined to influence Collete to join the robbery.

There is a rich deployment of language in the film. Jedidah herself easily switches from the Yoruba language to other languages depending on which of the sons she is addressing, and the sons themselves know a little of each other's language. This reverberates with my experience (2000) at the Lafia railway station where every child could speak up to 5 languages. When I observed further, I discovered that we had people from various ethnic nationalities living together in the railway quarters and that the children pick up the languages from their peers and environment as they grow up socializing together. Brown (1963) collaborates this point by asserting that:

While it is difficult for most adults to learn to speak a foreign language perfectly, that is without an accent, a child readily learns as its "native" language the one it hears spoken by the people around it as it first learns to speak. Any normal human being can easily learn to speak "like a native" in any language he hears from infancy.

This reinforces the theory of language as a "learned," and not an innate cultural trait (Lazaar, E 1999; Sapir, E.1985).

English, the Nigerian official language is deployed side by side with pidgin - the Nigerian variable of the English language. The film is rich in adage and proverbs. Jedidah's mantra, "What's gonna be, gonna be!" is a reflection of her life and others in *A Tribe Called Judah*. Even when she seems to know the long-term impact of her drinking, she is unable to break the habit and consequently, is suffering from kidney failure. In everything, she retorts, "Black don't crack!" which speaks to her resilience despite the many challenges life throws at her, and her deliberate effort to stay afloat. She recounts her experience to Linda and concludes "I did not bury myself." From her experience, she would advise to Bisi thus, "Rain will beat you...man na scam!"

In a confrontation with Daddy Michael, she berates him for beating his wife (Linda) by telling him, "The only thing that makes you a man is the one straw and 2 sack waters dangling under your trouser."

Collette punctuates her communication with her native Efik/Ibibio dialect when addressing her supervisees. We have such words as "Di mi" (come here), "udiongoke idem" (you are not sensitive), "dakka do" (get out of there), ka kenam utom (go and do your work), utebe mkpo (smelling thing), etc.

The rich Nigerian culture manifesting in a variety of costumes, music, dance, decoration, and make-up darts the costume party (1.17.50 -1.21.04). These reflect the cultural diversity of Nigeria, and the level of cultural tolerance of the people as we see patterns from the various ethnic offerings of the country.

Funke Akindede also showcases the complexities of Nigerian reality and the attempts at fusing modern trends in cultural development with traditional cultural patterns. These complexities come alive with security personnel collaborating with criminals, while others are making every effort to give a good account of their profession.

We see the Judah family leaving their grandmother in the hospital as they make to run away even without a word to her. This is sure a cultural shift from the traditional trend.

At the robbery scene, we notice that the armed robbers are using digital masks, as against conventional masks. The police are sending location with phone to colleagues for reinforcements.

There is also the portrayal of Nigeria as a huge consumer country, also of the persisting Japa syndrome where everyone is migrating overseas for education and greener pastures. The security officer at C&K Furniture has a visa to migrate to the US, even though he does not have the resources to pay for the flight ticket. Emeka has plans to travel overseas to Europe through Libya for education and self-actualization.

The Nigerian culture is presented as a highly masculine society. Daddy Michael is demanding to know who is giving the wife money to start the tomatoes and pepper market. When Jedidah intervenes, he retorts, "Keep quiet! I will ask all the questions...Don't you know that when a man is talking, you don't talk as a woman?" He goes further to threaten "...and if you don't stop talking, I will discipline you as I disciplined my wife." The decisiveness in Daddy Michael's articulation exudes competitiveness rather than collaboration with the wife, or appreciation to Jedidah for the support to the wife. According to Hofstede () a masculine culture stresses different expectations for men and women. In masculine culture, men are expected to be assertive, competitive, and focused on material success.

Halima's father is seeking to ascertain the paternity of Adamu and is asking straight-up questions, "You said, your father is from Dala local government area of Kano State. Which part of Dala local government is your father from, I mean, which family compound is your father from?" Even when Halima tries to interrupt him, he tells Adamu that they will continue to conversation. The masculine culture is also showcased through the character of Chigozie, the Chairman of C&K Furniture. When the Alaba office is visited by the task force, he is the one advising the wife to stay calm, while he is taking action to contain the visit. He is so focused on material wealth that he has given orders that his staff is wearing singlets and pants to count his money. He is into several businesses, is very selfless with his money, and even doing money laundering. He is keeping a gang of bad boys doing dirty jobs for him. He is killing A Boy for stealing his money.

Steven Spielberg's The Terminal

In Steven Spielberg's *The Terminal*, culture is explored through the lens of immigration and identity. Viktor Navoski (played by Tom Hanks), the main character in the film exposes us to the culture, first to the culture of the world's busiest airport and of the United States of America. We see thousands of passengers from various backgrounds, languages, and traditions converge, creating a vibrant tapestry of humanity. Travelers transiting through the airport, the checks at the various points, the stamping, the controls, and the security systems in place, the supporting businesses. The shared spaces, such as the check-in counters, security lines, and departure gates - become microcosms of global society. They provide an opportunity for cross-cultural connections as people from different cultural backgrounds meet

and interact on a broad spectrum of issues and interests enhanced by the general friendly disposition of everyone around the airport. The artwork, the architectural design, the cuisine, and the signages at the airport reflect the culture of the people, their advancement in art and science, and their aesthetic appeal and contribute to creating a beautiful cultural ambiance. We are also taken through some of the airport rituals such as removing shoes at security, scanning passports, and waiting at the gate. These shared experiences create a sense of belonging for travelers and remind us of the interconnectivity of the world and our shared humanity.

It mirrors the bureaucracy associated with our modern world. While Viktor was traveling to John F Kennedy's International Airport in New York, political crises erupted in his country – Krakozhia, toppling the government in place. This automatically rendered his international passport invalid as the Krakozhia lost her recognition under the American immigration law. Victor is now “stateless.” He cannot be allowed entry into the United States of America and neither can he be sent home and hence confined within the airport. Millions of people around the world are denied the right to a nationality, leaving them stateless. As a result, they may be unable to access other basic rights and services, such as being able to go to school, work legally, access health care, or get married. They are also often at a higher risk of exploitation and abuse (UNHCR 2024).

Viktor's language barrier becomes a central theme. He speaks Bulgarian as his native Krakozhian but also communicates in a constructed Slavic language resembling Bulgarian and Russian when helping a Russian-speaking passenger. The film accurately depicts the early and intermediate stages of second language acquisition, showing how naturalistic exposure can lead to language proficiency even for adult learners.

Viktor's limited skills in English, when he arrives at the airport, bring to the fore the place of language in cultural assimilation and adaptation to a new environment. On arrival at the airport, he is only able to tell the name of a local hotel and is unable to provide further details of his trip. With his extended stay at the airport, we see Victor hone his skills in English and begin to communicate effectively, even befriending some airport staff. He now has a better understanding of the crisis in his country. With his warm and friendly disposition, he helps Enrique express his love for Dolores, an immigration officer and to build a friendship with Amelia. In one of the most emotional scenes, Viktor is requested to help as a translator for a Russian man who is trying to take home an uncertificated medication for his sick father.

The film touches on the clash of cultures as passengers arrive at the airport from various countries of the world bringing with them their culture – language, dress, artifacts, values, and beliefs. While Amelia is always on the go and can't seem to sustain her relationships or job, Viktor is the exact opposite always staying on course whether with relationships or job. Viktor's interactions with airport staff, fellow travelers, and customs officials highlight cultural clashes. His background as a Krakozhian immigrant clashes with the American way of life, leading to humorous and poignant moments.

The public life of the American people is shown as aligning more with individualism as opposed to collectivism. In the film we see people mind their business, and value their independence and autonomy. Everyone strives to stand out with their work. It is difficult for Viktor to get help even with a phone call. Dixon is doing everything possible to get to the zenith of his professional career including trying his best to make Viktor another man's problem. *The Terminal's* America counts as a masculine country, which means that the society values competition, performance, and achievement. As a result, people tend to openly talk about their successes and status.

The film shows that America has zero tolerance for uncertainties. This is understandably so after the September 11, 2001, al-Qaeda attacks at the World Trade Center in New York City. We see functional security cameras everywhere at the airport, with eagle-eye security personnel providing surveillance. Sharper (2021) report:

"Before 9/11, security was almost invisible, and it was designed to be that way," Price says. "It was designed to be something in the background that wasn't that noticeable and did not interfere with aircraft or airport operations."

"You could walk up to the gate at the very last minute. You did not have to have a boarding pass," Price says. "All you had to do was go through the security checkpoint — no questions asked, no ID needed."

That forever changed on Tuesday, Sept. 11, 2001.

Now, travelers often stand in long lines at security checkpoints with wait times that can exceed an hour. We take off our shoes, empty our pockets, and take laptops and other devices out of carry-on bags before stepping into high-resolution, full-body scanners, while our bags go through 3D-imaging X-ray machines. And don't forget to take your liquids of 3.4 ounces or less out of your carry-on.

Checked baggage is screened by x-ray. Bomb detectors are employed with even pilots authorized to carry guns and more security personnel are deployed to the airports.

Power distance - the extent to which a society expects equality among its members is low in America with the society seeking more equal power distribution. From the cleaners at the airport to the most senior officer, we see everyone's power at a nearly equal distribution. One is responsible for his or her beat, and sticking to the rules.

America in the film is shown to have a culture of long-term planning. This is obvious in the design of the massive design of the airport, the various systems setups, and the various interventions we see. People know what to do at every point, unlike the situation in countries without plans for exigencies. America did not waste time in seizing to recognize Krakozhia following to crisis that led to the dissolution of the seating government. Viktor is provided meal tickets and a calling card to help him cope with his confinement. Mr. Dixxon would need Viktor to break a law for him to be able to get him out of the airport. Viktor could make money for his food while at the airport collecting luggage carts. He needed an appointment to recover his meal tickets from the Indian American Janitor.

The film delves into the challenges faced by immigrants. Viktor's resilience, adaptability, and determination to survive in a foreign land resonate with the immigrants' experience. Viktor's prolonged stay at the airport emphasizes the feeling of being stranded, both physically and culturally. His inability to leave the terminal reflects the liminal space between cultures. He befriends Enrique (played by Diego Luna), a food service worker, and falls for Amelia Warren (played by Catherine Zeta-Jones), a flight attendant. He forms unlikely friendships with people like Gupta (played by Kumar Pallana), a janitor, and Dolores (played by Zoe Saldana), a customs officer.

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